

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Acetophenone by Chloramine-T in Acid Medium

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The kinetic measurements of the oxidation of acetophenone have been made in 25% aqueous acetic acid. The oxidation reaction is first order each in ketone and chloramine-T. The first order rate constant k_1 is proportional to $[H^+]$. Effect of neutral salt viz. $NaClO_4$ and KCl shows the reaction to exhibit a positive salt effect. Arrhenius parameters have been computed. The mechanism has been proposed on the basis of experimental results.

CHLORAMINE-T has been widely used for the oxidation of a large number of organic compounds¹, however very few papers are available on the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of reducing substrates²⁻⁸. Osmium catalysed oxidation of acetone and ethylmethylketone by Chloramine-T has been reported by Mushran and coworkers⁹. In another communication Bose, Ram Sanehi and Mushran have discussed the oxidation mechanism of cyclopentanone by Chloramine-T, in alkaline medium¹⁰.

In the present communication the kinetics of the oxidation of acetophenone is 25% HOAc - 75% H₂O (Vol/Vol).

Experimental

B.D.H. samples of Acetophenone and Chloramine-T were used for present investigations. All other chemicals used were also of AR, BDH or extra pure quality and their solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water. In all the experiments vessels of pyrex or Jena Glass were used. The reaction vessels were coated with black Japan to eliminate the photochemical effect, if any. The kinetic measurements were made by estimating the aliquot portions of reaction mixtures for Chloramine-T iodometrically using starch as indicator.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of the oxidation of acetophenone by Chloramine-T has been investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants in presence of fixed amount of acetic acid. The kinetic observations were recorded for the completion of 60-80% reactions. Good first order rate constants were obtained which were linear at all concentrations of ketone. The plot of $\log k_1$ against $\log(\text{Acetophenone})$ gave straight line the slope of which was found unity (Fig. 1), which stabilises a first order dependence in acetophenone concentration.

The second order rate constant $k_2 = \frac{k_1}{[\text{Acetophenone}]}$ were calculated and the average value was found to be

$2.21 \times 10^{-1} \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$. for the oxidation of acetophenone. Pseudo first order rate constants in Chloramine-T were calculated from the slope of the log-time plots. Results of table-1 record a slight fall in k_1 values with the increase of Chloramine-T. This is due to the hydrolysis of Chloramine-T giving rise to Toluene sulphonamide which retards the oxidation¹¹. Some deviation is also due to the formation of $NaClO_4$, as reported by earlier workers in Chloramino-metric reactions.

Fig. 1

Dielectric constant effect. : The reaction has been studied in acetic acid water binary mixtures. Increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the reaction mixture increases the rate of oxidation (Table-2). This is due to the lowering of dielectric constant of the medium which favours reactions involving protonation¹².

TABLE 1. EFFECT OF REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS AT 50°.

10^4 [Chloramine-T] M	10^2 [Acetophenone] M	$k_1 \times 10^8$ Min. ⁻¹	$k_2 \times 10$ 1. mole ⁻¹ min. ⁻¹
2.0	3.0	6.76	2.25
2.2	3.0	6.69	2.23
2.4	3.0	6.64	2.21
2.6	3.0	6.61	2.20
2.8	3.0	5.91	1.97
3.0	3.0	6.60	2.35
3.0	1.9	4.19	2.21
3.0	2.0	4.55	2.27
3.0	2.2	4.83	2.19
3.0	2.4	5.31	2.21
3.0	2.6	5.59	2.16
3.0	2.8	6.40	2.28
3.0	3.0	6.76	2.25

In presence of 25% HOAC-75% H₂O(vol./vol).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING HOAC CONCENTRATIONS

% HOAC	$k_1 \times 10^8$ min ⁻¹
10	1.89
20	2.38
30	2.80
40	3.25
50	3.52
60	4.01
70	4.49
80	4.70

Temperature = 40°C

[Acetophenone] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ [Chloramine-T] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Effect of neutral salt : The kinetic runs were made at 50° with varying concentrations of neutral salts such as KCl and NaClO₄ keeping the concentration of substrate and the oxidant constant. The results tabulated in Table 3 indicate that the reaction exhibits positive salt effect.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF NEUTRAL SALTS ON RATES

Salt. M.	$k \times 10^{-3}$ min. ⁻¹	
	KCl	NaClO ₄
0.10	5.43	6.43
0.030	6.61	7.42
0.050	7.61	7.90
0.080	8.59	7.66
0.10	10.20	9.82
0.15	12.82	11.90

Temp. 50°C. Solvent : 50% HOAC
[Acetophenone] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$
[Chloramine-T] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Temperature effect : The kinetic runs were made at 0.03 M acetophenone and in the temperature range of 40 to 60°. The ϵ_{act} , calculated from the slope of the Arrhenius plot is obtained as 17.19 K.Cal./mole. From this the values of log A and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are calculated out as 8.57 and -25.9 e.u.

Effect of variation of acid concentration : Runs were carried out at 50° keeping the concentration of acetophenone and chloramine-T constant at varied concentrations of hydrochloric acid. The results of Table 4 indicate that the first order rate constant k_1 is proportional to (H⁺).

TABLE 4—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON ACID

$[H^+] \times 10^3$ M	$k_1 \times 10^3$, min. ⁻¹	$k_2 = \frac{k_1}{[H^+]}$.1. mol. ⁻¹ min. ⁻¹
2.5	2.52	1.08
5.0	4.96	0.99
15.0	15.06	1.04
20.0	21.30	1.065
25.0	26.93	1.09

Temp. = 30°

Solvent = 25% HOAC

[Acetophenone] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ [Chloramine-T] = $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

On the basis of the experimental results we propose the oxidation of acetophenone to benzoic acid as a reaction between the enol form of the ketone and HOCl. The presence of benzoic acid has been detected in the reaction product by usual tests.

Mushran, Mehrotra and Sanehi¹³ have shown that the oxidising properties of chloramine-T may be due to four oxidising species viz. Chloramine-T itself, or *p*-toluene sulphochloramide or dichloramine T or hypochlorite ion which are the hydrolytic products of the oxidant. Since the first order rate constants show a linear dependence on (H⁺) concentration (Table 4) the formation of HOCl as a slow step is obvious as shown below

The dependence of first order rate constants on acid concentrations is also attributed to the formation of the conjugate acid of the acetophenone as a fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer.

This conjugate acid species of acetophenone gives its enol form by the action of water bimolecularly.

The reaction of the enol form of ketone with HOCl to give products is the slow and rate determining step :

It is concluded that during the oxidation of acetophenone by Chloramine-T in acid medium, the rate determining step involves the reaction between the enol form of the ketone and HOCl formed as shown in steps 1 to 5.

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